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JIS **Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)**

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

The journey towards the publication of Volume 3, Issue 1 in May 2019 commenced from the day of publication of JIS's previous issue in November 2018. Notably, the editorial column has gained a wider readership community from the academic platform. The publication of volumes and issues are not straightforward tasks but the interest in serving academia generates a motivation to continue to promote scholarship based on important research studies. The best possible course of action is always realized after the outcome of the previous action. In every issue published by JIS, the editors are constantly communicating with the corresponding authors to strengthen the academic collaboration amongst and between the author(s) and the JIS editorial. This type of collegiality can be described as a journey towards enriching beautiful minds towards intelligent minds.

On this note, I wish to announce the publication of the current Volume 3, Issue 1 for release in May 2019. In this issue, interdisciplinary scientific research papers are published, which comes from various disciplines including Education, Social Sciences, Philosophy, Psychology and Medical Sciences.

The JIS is constantly committed to serve the authors and readers with free download access, free submissions and free publication. Our next issue will be published as scheduled in November 2019 and we invite scholars from various disciplines to submit their scientific papers.

On a final note, I wish to extend many thanks to the reviewers of this May 2019 Issue. We always provide a separate content's page to publish the reviewers' names for supporting the journal by providing constructive comments and suggestions in a timeous manner and to maintain the quality of scientific and academic publication.

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
Founder and Editor-in-Chief
Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Table of content

Editorial	iv
Interdisciplinary Sequences: A Conceptual Commentary <i>Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari</i>	1
Differences in 2-Year Persistence Rates by Student Institutional Status for Black Texas Community College Students: A Statewide, Multiyear Investigation <i>Sheldon Moss and John R. Slate</i>	9
Differences in the Perception of Educational Benefits between Male and Female Veterans in the United States: A National Study <i>Cassandra D. Boyd, John R. Slate and Wally Barnes</i>	27
Wandering Through the Desert with Multiple Sclerosis: How Outdoor Life Recalibrates Body Awareness and Self-Identity <i>Joeri Calsius, Minne Van Den Noortgate, Gert Roncada, Paul Van Asch and Marie D'hooghe</i>	37
Quantum Words and Newtonian Sentences, Structure of Language and Algebra <i>William L. Abler</i>	56
The Importance of Student's Representation in the Governance Structure of Historically Black Universities in South Africa <i>Felix Omal</i>	78
The Analysis of the Relationship between Personality Characteristics and Auricular Anatomy <i>Rengin Kosif, Murat Diramali, and Selin Yilmaz</i>	88
International Interdisciplinary Collaboration: Artisanal and Small Scale Gold Mining and Mercury Contamination in Colombia <i>Mateo S. Pimentel, Cristian A. Flórez and Oscar Jaime Restrepo Bae</i>	96
Acknowledgement to reviewers <i>From the Desk of Editor-in-Chief</i>	113